

Determination of Bioactive Chemical Composition of Methanolic Leaves Extract of *Sinapis arvensis* Using GC-MS Technique

Abeer Fauzi Al-Rubaye¹, Mohanad Jawad Kadhim², Imad Hadi Hameed^{3*}

¹Department of Biology, College of Science for women, University of Babylon, Iraq

²College of Biotechnology, Department of Genetic Engineering, Al-Qasim Green University, Iraq

³College of Nursing, University of Babylon, Iraq

Available Online: 1st May, 2017

ABSTRACT

Plants play an important role in providing food for humans. Among plants economic significance medicinal and aromatic plants which played a critical where it used as therapeutic agents to a long time. Thirty bioactive phytochemical compounds were identified in the methanolic extract of *Sinapis arvensis*: Erythritol, Nitro-2-propanol, Cyclopentanemethylamine, 2-isopropylidene-N,N,5-trimethyl, Furfural, 3-(1,3-Dihydroxyisopropyl)-1,5,8,11-tetraoxacyclotridecane, 3-Azabutyl-1-ol, 4-cyclopropyl-3,3-dimethyl-bromide, 1-Butene, 4-isothiocyanato-, 2,4-Difluorobenzene, 1-benzyloxy-, Eicosanoic acid, phenylmethyl ester, α -D-Glucopyranoside, O- α -D-glucopyranosyl-(1.fwdarw.3)- β -, Trigonelline, 4H-Pyran-4-one, 2,3-dihydro-3,5-dihydroxy-6-methyl, Estragole, Pentanenitrile, 5-(methylthio)-, 5-Hydroxymethylfurfural, Eugenol, Maltose, 2H-Thiopyran-3,5-diol, tetrahydro-4-nitro-, monoacetate (ester), Tetraacetyl-d-xylonic nitrile, 3,6-Diazahomoadamantan-9-one Hydrzone, 9,10-Secocholesta-5,7,10(19)-triene-3,24,25-triol, (3 β ,5Z,7E)-, 13-Heptadecyn-1-ol, Tributyl acetylcitrate, E)-13-Docosenoic acid, Phthalic acid, decyl oct-3-yl ester, γ -Tocopherol, Desoxo-9x-hydroxy-7-ketoingol 3,8,9,12-tetraacetate, Campesterol, γ -Sitosterol. The identification of phytochemical compounds is based on the peak area, retention time molecular weight, molecular formula, MS Fragment- ions and Pharmacological actions.

Keywords: Anti-microbial, Chemical composition, *Sinapis arvensis*.

INTRODUCTION

Natural products of higher plants be possible provide a new source of antimicrobial agents with maybe novel mechanisms of activity. In developing countries, *Sinapis arvensis* L. are used as fodder to livestock, food and folklore medicine. Brassicaceae (the mustard family) is a large family comprising 3,700 species spread over 338 genera¹⁻⁴. *S. arvensis* is native to Europe and grows wildly in western Asia, North Africa and throughout much of North America^{5,6}. The difference between family members are in having a pungent flavor and sulfury odor lead to the volatile isothiocyanate derivatives, acquired upon hydrolysis of glucosinolate. *Sinapis* (mustard), a genus of Brassicaceae, has a long history of use as condiments and as herbal medicines. In many developing countries, *Sinapis* species are used as food, fodder to livestock, and in folklore medicine⁷⁻¹³. This genus comprises six annual species: *Sinapis alba* L. (white mustard), *S. arvensis* L. (wild mustard), *S. flexuosa* Poir., *S. pubescens* L., *S. recurvata* All., and *S. setigera* J. Gay ex Lange¹⁴. Many microorganisms caused the infectious are resistant to drugs synthetic, therefore, an optional therapy is much required and pull toward the attention of many researchers the worldwide. The family has a worldwide distribution, but mostly in the Northern temperate regions and strikingly diverse around the

Mediterranean. Economic importance includes numerous vegetable and flavoring plants that are of major interest for human health and nutrition^{15,16}. Members of the family are distinctive in having a pungent flavor and sulfury odor due to the volatile isothiocyanate derivatives, obtained upon hydrolysis of glucosinolates¹⁷.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant material and extraction

The leaves of *Sinapis arvensis* were dried at room temperature for ten days and when properly dried then powdered using clean pestle and mortar, and the powdered plant was size reduced with a sieve. About fifteen grams of the plant sample powdered were soaked in 100 mL methanol individually. The isolated extracts were re-suspended in a minimum required volume of corresponding solvents and placed on the water bath at 60 C° to evaporate the extra solvents for the isolation of pure extracts¹⁸⁻⁴⁰. Then all the extracts were preserved in separate containers at 5 C° for further experimentations.

Gas chromatography – Mass Spectrum analysis

Sinapis arvensis GC-MS analysis were carried out in a GC system (Agilent 7890 Aseries, USA). The flow rate of the carrier gas, helium (He) was set to be 1 mL min⁻¹, split ratio was 1:50. The injector temperature was adjusted at 250°C, while the detector temperature was

fixed to 280°C. The column temperature was kept at 40°C for 1 min followed by linear programming to raise the temperature from 40°C to 120°C (at 4°C min⁻¹ with 2 min hold time), 120°C to 170°C (at 6°C min⁻¹ with 1 min hold time) and 170°C to 200°C (at 10°C min⁻¹ with 1 min hold time). The transfer line was heated at 280°C. Two microliter of FAME sample was injected for analysis⁴¹⁻⁵². Mass spectra were acquired in scan mode (70 eV); in the range of 50–550 m/z. Identification of compounds interpretation of mass spectrum was conducted using the database of National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST, USA). The database consists of more than 62,000 patterns of known compounds. The spectrum of the extract was matched with the spectrum of the known components stored in the NIST library⁵³⁻⁵⁶.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Plants are very important resource due to produce complex molecular. The plant produce structures such as secondary metabolism and their derivatives have antimicrobial properties, such as alkaloids, phenolic compounds, terpenes, tannins, coumarins, flavonoids, isoflavonoids and glycosides⁵⁷⁻⁶⁰. Gas chromatography and mass spectroscopy analysis of compounds was carried out in methanolic leaves extract of *Sinapis arvensis*, shown in Table 1. The GC-MS chromatogram of the 30 peaks of the compounds detected was shown in Figure 1. Chromatogram GC-MS analysis of the methanol extract of *Sinapis arvensis* showed the presence of thirty major peaks and the components corresponding to the peaks were determined as follows. Erythritol, Nitro-2-propanol, Cyclopentanemethylamine, 2-isopropylidene-N,N,5-trimethyl, Furfural, 3-(1,3-Dihydroxyisopropyl)-1,5,8,11-tetraoxacyclotridecane, 3-Azabutyl-1-ol, 4-cyclopropyl-3,3-dimethyl-bromide, 1-Butene, 4-isothiocyanato-, 2,4-Difluorobenzene, 1-benzyloxy-, Eicosanoic acid, phenylmethyl ester, α -D-Glucopyranoside, O- α -D-glucopyranosyl-(1-fwdarw.3)- β -Trigonelline, 4H-Pyran-4-one, 2,3-dihydro-3,5-dihydroxy-6-methyl, Estragole, Pentanenitrile, 5-(methylthio)-, 5-Hydroxymethylfurfural, Eugenol, Maltose, 2H-Thiopyran-3,5-diol, tetrahydro-4-nitro-monoacetate (ester), Tetraacetyl-d-xylonic nitrile, 3,6-Diazahomoadamantan-9-one, Hydrazone, 9,10-Secocholesta-5,7,10(19)-triene-3,24,25-triol, (3 β ,5Z,7E)-, 13-Heptadecyn-1-ol, Tributyl acetylcitrate, E)-13-Docosenoic acid, Phthalic acid, decyl oct-3-yl ester, γ -Tocopherol, Desoxo-9 α -hydroxy-7-ketoingol, 3,8,9,12-tetraacetate, Campesterol, γ -Sitosterol.

CONCLUSION

Sinapis arvensis is native plant of Iraq. In the present study determined that forty six phytoconstituents were identified from methanol leaves extract of *Sinapis arvensis* by gas chromatogram and mass spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis. *Sinapis arvensis* leaves can be used as a promising multipurpose medicinal source whereas further clinical trial is required to prove its efficacy.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors thank the department of biology in college of nursing for providing all necessary facilities to conduct this study. Authors also thank Assist. Prof. Dr. Ameen Al-yasiri for assisting in extract preparation, and biochemical analysis.

REFERENCES

1. Cordell GA. Changing strategies in natural products chemistry. A review cordifolia leaves. *Phytother. Res.* 1995; 4: 198-200.
2. Barbour EK, AlSharif M, Sagherian VK, Habre AN, Talhouk RS, Talhouk SN. Screening of selected indigenous plants of Lebanon for antimicrobial activity. *J. Ethnopharmacol.* 2004; 93: 1-7.
3. Hamil FA, Apio S, Mubiru NK, Bukenya-Ziraba R, Mosango M, Maganyi OW *et al.* Traditional herbal drugs of Southern Uganda, II: literature analysis and antimicrobial assays. *J. Ethnopharmacol.* 2003; 84: 57- 78.
4. Motsei ML, Machado TB, Pinto AV, Pinto MCFR, Leal ICR, Silva MG, *et al.* In-vitro activity of Brazilian medicinal plants, naturally occurring naphthoquinones and their analogues, against methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Int. J. Antimicrob.* 2003; 21: 279-284.
5. Kadhim MJ, Sosa AA, Hameed IH. Evaluation of anti-bacterial activity and bioactive chemical analysis of *Ocimum basilicum* using Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) and gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) techniques. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemical Research.* 2016; 8(6): 127-146.
6. Mohammed GJ, Kadhim MJ, Hussein HM. Characterization of bioactive chemical compounds from *Aspergillus terreus* and evaluation of antibacterial and antifungal activity. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemical Research.* 2016; 8(6): 889-905.
7. Chew YL, Goh JK, Lim YY. Assessment of in vitro antioxidant capacity and polyphenolic composition of selected medicinal herbs from Leguminosae family in Peninsular Malaysia. *Food Chem.* 2009; 116, 13-18.
8. Hashem FA, Saleh MM. Antimicrobial components of some Cruciferae plants (*Diplotaxis harra* Forssk. and *Erucaria microcarpa* Boiss). *Phytother. Res.* 1999; 13(4): 329-332.
9. Lin CM, Preston F, Wei C. Antibacterial mechanism of allyl isothiocyanate. *J. Food Prot.* 2006; 3: 727–734.
10. Afsharypuor S, Balam MH. Essential Oil Constituents of Leaves and Fruits of *Pinus eldarica*. *Med. J. Essent. Oil Res.* 2005; 17: 440–441.
11. Al-Qudah MA, Abu Zarga MH. Chemical composition of essential oils from aerial parts of *Sisymbrium irio* L. from Jordan. *E-J Chemi.* 2010; 7(1): 6- 10.
12. Bendimerad N, Bendiab SAT, Breme K, Fernandez X. Essential oil composition of aerial parts of *Sinapis*

Figure 6: Mass spectrum of 3-(1,3-Dihydroxyisopropyl)-1,5,8,11-tetraoxacyclotridecane with Retention Time (RT)= 3.957

Figure 7: Mass spectrum of 3-Azabutyl-1-ol, 4-cyclopropyl-3,3-dimethyl-, bromide with Retention Time (RT)= 4.191

Figure 8: Mass spectrum of 1-Butene, 4-isothiocyanato- with Retention Time (RT)= 4.420

Figure 9: Mass spectrum of 2,4-Difluorobenzene, 1-benzyloxy- with Retention Time (RT)= 4.632

Figure 10: Mass spectrum of Eicosanoic acid, phenylmethyl ester with Retention Time (RT)= 4.832

Figure 11: Mass spectrum of α -D-Glucopyranoside, O- α -D-glucopyranosyl-(1.fwdarw.3)- β -D-glucopyranoside with Retention Time (RT)= 5.021

Figure 12: Mass spectrum of Trigonelline with Retention Time (RT)= 5.530

Figure 13: Mass spectrum of 4H-Pyran-4-one, 2,3-dihydro-3,5-dihydroxy-6-methyl- with Retention Time (RT)= 5.673

Figure 14: Mass spectrum of Estragole with Retention Time (RT)= 5.965

Figure 15: Mass spectrum of Pentanenitrile, 5-(methylthio)- with Retention Time (RT)= 6.034

Figure 16: Mass spectrum of 5-Hydroxymethylfurfural with Retention Time (RT)= 6.434

Figure 17: Mass spectrum of Eugenol with Retention Time (RT)= 7.470

Figure 18: Mass spectrum of Maltose with Retention Time (RT)= 7.750

Figure 19: Mass spectrum of 2H-Thiopyran-3,5-diol, tetrahydro-4-nitro-, monoacetate (ester) with Retention Time (RT)= 8.305

Figure 20: Mass spectrum of Tetraacetyl-d-xyliconic nitrile with Retention Time (RT)= 9.558

Figure 21: Mass spectrum of 3,6-Diazahomoadamantan-9-one Hydrazone with Retention Time (RT)= 9.753

Figure 22: Mass spectrum of 9,10-Secocholesta-5,7,10(19)-triene-3,24,25-triol, (3β,5Z,7E)- with Retention Time (RT)= 13.478

Figure 23: Mass spectrum of 13-Heptadecyn-1-ol with Retention Time (RT)= 14.720

Figure 24: Mass spectrum of Tributyl acetylacrylate with Retention Time (RT)= 16.390

Figure 25: Mass spectrum of Cyproheptadine with Retention Time (RT)= 17.804

Figure 26: Mass spectrum of (E)-13-Docosenoic acid with Retention Time (RT)= 18.799

Figure 27: Mass spectrum of Phthalic acid, decyl oct-3-yl ester with Retention Time (RT)= 21.924

Figure 28: Mass spectrum of γ -Tocopherol with Retention Time (RT)= 22.307

Figure 29: Mass spectrum of 9-Desoxo-9x-hydroxy-7-ketoingol 3,8,9,12-tetraacetate with Retention Time (RT)= 22.850

Table 1. Major phytochemical compounds identified in methanolic extract of *Sinapis arvensis*.

Serial No.	Phytochemical compound	RT (min)	Molecular Weight	Exact Mass	Chemical structure	MS Fragmentations	Pharmacological actions
1.	Erythritol	3.287	122	122.057909		61,74,91	Anti-Bacterial Agents
2.	1-Nitro-2-propanol	3.424	105	105.042593		61,69,90,104	Anti-Bacterial Agents
3.	Cyclopentanemethylamine, 2-isopropylidene-N,N,5-trimethyl-,	3.476	181	181.18305		58,81,107,136,164	anti-inflammatory
4.	Furfural	3.665	96	96.021129		51,67,96	anti-tyrosinase activity
5.	3-(1,3-Dihydroxyisopropyl)-1,5,8,11-tetraoxacyclotridecane	3.957	264	264.157288		54,67,89,113,151,177,216,264	anti-cancer activity

6.	3-Azabutyl-1-ol,4-cyclopropyl-3,3-dimethyl-,bromide	4.191	144	144.138839		55,98,129,144	New chemical compound
7.	1-Butene , 4- isothiocyanato-	4.420	113	113.02992		55,72,85,113	Antioxidant Activities
8.	2,4-Difluorobenzene , 1- benzyloxy-	4.632	220	220.069971		65,91,129,157	antitumor, anti-inflammatory
9.	Eicosanoic acid , 4- phenylmethyl ester	4.832	402	402.349781		57,71,91,108,1 26,147,207,281	Anti-inflammatory
10.	α -D-Glucopyranoside ,O- α -D-glucopyranosyl- (1.fwdarw.3)- β -	5.021	504	504.169035		60,73,85,97,12 6,145,199	anti-inflammatory, antistress

11.	Trigonelline	5.530	137	137.047678		51,78,106,137	antibacterial, antiviral, and anti-tumor activities
12	4H-Pyran-4-one ,2,3-dihydro-3,5-dihydroxy-6-methyl-	5.673	144	144.042258		55,72,101,115,144	antibacterial activities and antioxidant
13	Estragole	5.965	148	148.088815		51,63,77,91,121,148	anti-inflammatory activity
14	Pentanenitrile (methylthio)-	6.034	129	129.06122		55,61,82,114,129	anti-inflammatory and antitumor activities
15	5-Hydroxymethylfurfural	6.434	126	126.031694		53,69,97,126	antioxidant and anti-proliferative activities

16	Eugenol	7.470	164	164.08373		55,65,77,91,103,149,164	antioxidant, anti-inflammatory	
17	Maltose	7.750	342	342.11621		60,73,85,97,126,163	anti-inflammatory and analgesic effect	
18	2H-Thiopyran-3,5-diol, tetrahydro-4-nitro-, monoacetate (ester)	8.305	221	221.035793		57,85,115,161,221	anti-inflammatory	
19	Tetraacetyl-d-xylonic nitrile	9.558	343	343.090332		60,73,112,133,238,281	antimicrobial, antioxidant	

20	3,6-Diazahomoadamantan-9-one Hydrazone	9.753	180	180.137497		58,72,95,121,1 64,180	antiviral effect
21	9,10-Secocholesta-5,7,10(19)-triene-3,24,25-triol, (3 β ,5Z,7E)-	13.478	416	416.329044		55,136,158,207 ,253,383,416	Unknown
22	13-Heptadecyn-1-ol	14.720	252	252.245316		55,67,82,96,21 9	anti-inflammatory, antifungal
23	Tributyl acetylcitrate	16.390	402	402.225368		57,112,129,157 ,185,213,259,3 29	antioxidant and anti-inflammatory
25	(E)-13-Docosenoic acid	18.799	338	338.318481		55,69,98,222,3 20,338	antimicrobial activity

26	Phthalic acid , decyl oct-3-yl ester	21.924	418	418.30831		57,104,149,193,251,307	anti-bacterial activity
27	γ -Tocopherol	22.307	416	416.36543		57,69,107,151,191,246,288,330,372,416	Anti-inflammatory
28	9-Desoxo-9x-hydroxy-7-ketoingol 3,8,9,12-tetraacetate	22.850	534	534.2465		69,109,137,223,312,372,432,459,534	New chemical compound
29	Campesterol	23.531	400	400.370516		55,81,145,213,255,289,315,400	anti-inflammatory activity
30	γ -Sitosterol	24.121	414	414.386166		55,81,145,213,255,273,303,329,396,414	anti-inflammatory activity

Figure 30: Mass spectrum of Campesterol with Retention Time (RT)= 23.531

Figure 31: Mass spectrum of γ -Sitosterol with Retention Time (RT)= 24.121

arvensis L. from Algeria, *Essent. Oil Res.* 2007; 19(3): 206–208.

13. Mhaskar KS, Blatter E, Caius JF, Kirtikar Basu's Illustrated Indian Medicinal plants. Delhi, Satguru Publication .2000; 1455-1457.
14. Vaghasiya Y, Nair R, Chanda S. Antibacterial and preliminary Phytochemical and physio-chemical analysis of *Eucalyptus citriodora* Hk leaf. *Nat. Prod. Research* 2008; 22: 754-762.
5. Sinclair A. Remedies for common family ailments: 10 Nasal decongestants. *Prof. Care Mother Child.* 1996; 6(1):9-11.
15. Silva J, Abebe W, Sousa SM , Duarte VG, Machado MI , Matos FJ. Analgesic and anti-inflammatory effects of essential oils of *Eucalyptus*. *J. Ethnopharmacol.* 2003; 89: 277-283.
16. Ramezani H. Fungicidal activity of volatile oil from *Eucalyptus citriodora* Hook. against *Alternaria triticina*. *Commun Agric. Appl Biol Sci* 2006; 71: 909-914.
17. Clemente MA, de Oliveira Monteiro CM, Scoralik MG, Gomes FT, de Azevedo Prala M.C. Acricidal activity of the essential oils from *Eucalyptus citriodora* and *Cymbopogon nardus* on larvae of *Amblyomma cajennense* (Acari: Ixodidae) and *Anocentor nitens* (Acari: Ixodidae). *Parasitol. Research.* 2010; 107: 987-992.
18. Hameed IH, Altameme HJ, Idan SA. *Artemisia annua*: Biochemical products analysis of methanolic aerial parts extract and anti-microbial capacity. *Research Journal of Pharmaceutical, Biological and Chemical Sciences.* 2016; 7(2): 1843- 1868
19. Hussein AO, Mohammed GJ, Hadi MY, Hameed IH. Phytochemical screening of methanolic dried galls extract of *Quercus infectoria* using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) and Fourier transform-infrared (FT-IR). *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy.* 2016; 8(3): 49-59.
20. Sosa AA, Bagi SH, Hameed IH. Analysis of bioactive chemical compounds of *Euphorbia lathyris* using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry and fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemical Research.* 2016; 8(5): 109-126.
21. Altameme HJ, Hadi MY, Hameed IH. Phytochemical analysis of *Urtica dioica* leaves by fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy and gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy.* 2015; 7(10): 238-252.
22. Mohammed GJ, Omran AM, Hussein HM. Antibacterial and Phytochemical Analysis of *Piper nigrum* using Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrum and Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemical Research.* 2016; 8(6): 977-996.
23. Hamza LF, Kamal SA, Hameed IH. Determination of metabolites products by *Penicillium expansum* and evaluating antimicrobial activity. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy.* 2015; 7(9): 194-220.
24. Jasim H, Hussein AO, Hameed IH, Kareem MA. Characterization of alkaloid constitution and evaluation of antimicrobial activity of *Solanum nigrum* using gas chromatography mass spectrometry (GC-MS). *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy.* 2015; 7(4): 56-72.
25. Hadi MY, Mohammed GJ, Hameed IH. Analysis of bioactive chemical compounds of *Nigella sativa* using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy.* 2016; 8(2): 8-24.
26. Hameed IH, Ibraheam IA, Kadhim HJ. Gas chromatography mass spectrum and fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy analysis of methanolic extract of *Rosmarinus officinalis* leaves. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy.* 2015; 7(6): 90-106.
27. Shareef HK, Muhammed HJ, Hussein HM, Hameed IH. Antibacterial effect of ginger (*Zingiber officinale*) roscoe and bioactive chemical analysis using gas chromatography mass spectrum. *Oriental Journal of Chemistry.* 2016; 32(2): 20-40.
28. Al-Jassaci MJ, Mohammed GJ, Hameed IH. Secondary Metabolites Analysis of *Saccharomyces*

- cerivisiae* and Evaluation of Antibacterial Activity. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*. 2016; 8(5): 304-315.
29. Mohammed GJ, Al-Jassani MJ, Hameed IH. Antibacterial, Antifungal Activity and Chemical analysis of *Punica grantanum* (Pomegranate peel) using GC-MS and FTIR spectroscopy. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemical Research*. 2016; 8(3): 480-494.
30. Al-Marzoqi AH, Hadi MY, Hameed IH. Determination of metabolites products by *Cassia angustifolia* and evaluate antimicrobial activity. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2016; 8(2): 25-48.
31. Altameme HJ, Hameed IH, Abu-Serag NA. Analysis of bioactive phytochemical compounds of two medicinal plants, *Equisetum arvense* and *Alchemilla vulgaris* seed using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry and fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy. *Malays. Appl. Biol*. 2015; 44(4): 47-58.
32. Hameed IH, Hamza LF, Kamal SA. Analysis of bioactive chemical compounds of *Aspergillus niger* by using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry and fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2015;7(8): 132-163.
33. Hameed IH, Hussein HJ, Kareem MA, Hamad NS. Identification of five newly described bioactive chemical compounds in methanolic extract of *Mentha viridis* by using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS). *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2015; 7 (7): 107-125.
34. Hussein HM, Hameed IH, Ibraheem OA. Antimicrobial Activity and spectral chemical analysis of methanolic leaves extract of *Adiantum Capillus-Veneris* using GC-MS and FT-IR spectroscopy. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemical Research*. 2016; 8(3): 369-385.
35. Hussein HJ, Hadi MY, Hameed IH. Study of chemical composition of *Foeniculum vulgare* using Fourier transform infrared spectrophotometer and gas chromatography - mass spectrometry. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2016; 8(3): 60-89.
36. Kadhim MJ, Mohammed GJ, Hameed IH. In vitro antibacterial, antifungal and phytochemical analysis of methanolic fruit extract of *Cassia fistula*. *Oriental Journal of Chemistry*. 2016; 32(2): 10-30.
37. Altameme HJ, Hameed IH, Idan SA, Hadi MY. Biochemical analysis of *Origanum vulgare* seeds by fourier-transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy and gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS). *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2015; 7(9): 221-237.
38. Hussein HM. Determination of phytochemical composition and ten elements content (CD, CA, CR, CO, FE, PB, MG, MN, NI AND ZN) of *CARDARIA DRABA* by GC-MS, FT-IR and AAS technique. *Int. J Pharm Bio Sci*. 2016; 7(3): (B) 1009 -1017.
39. Hussein HM. Analysis of trace heavy metals and volatile chemical compounds of *Lepidium sativum* using atomic absorption spectroscopy, gas chromatography-mass spectrometric and fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy. *Research Journal of Pharmaceutical, Biological and Chemical Sciences*. 2016; 7(4): 2529 - 2555.
40. Hameed IH. A new polymorphic positions discovered in mitochondrial DNA hypervariable region HVIII from central and north-central of Iraq. *Mitochondrial DNA*. 2016; 27(5): 3250-4.
41. Jaddoa HH, Hameed IH, Mohammed GJ. Analysis of volatile metabolites released by *Staphylococcus aureus* using gas chromatography-Mass spectrometry and determination of its antifungal activity. *Orient J Chem*. 2016; 32(4).
42. Hameed IH, Salman HD, Mohammed GJ. Evaluation of antifungal and antibacterial activity and analysis of bioactive phytochemical compounds of *Cinnamomum zeylanicum* (Cinnamon bark) using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. *Orient J Chem*. 2016; 32(4).
43. Hameed IH, Jebor MA, Ommer AJ, Abdulzahra AI. Haplotype data of mitochondrial DNA coding region encompassing nucleotide positions 11,719-12,184 and evaluate the importance of these positions for forensic genetic purposes in Iraq. *Mitochondrial DNA*. 2016; 27(2): 1324-1327.
44. Kadhim MJ, Mohammed GJ, Hussein HM. Analysis of bioactive metabolites from *Candida albicans* using (GC-MS) and evaluation of antibacterial activity. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*. 2016; 8(7): 655-670.
45. Mohammad A, Imad H. Autosomal STR: From locus information to next generation sequencing technology. *Research Journal of Biotechnology*. 2013.
46. Hameed, I.H., Abdulzahra, A.I., Jebor, M.A., Kqueen, C.Y., Ommer, A.J. Haplotypes and variable position detection in the mitochondrial DNA coding region encompassing nucleotide positions 10,716-11,184. *Mitochondrial DNA*. 2015.
47. Ubaid JM, Hussein HM, Hameed IH. Analysis of bioactive compounds of *Tribolium castaneum* and evaluation of anti-bacterial activity. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*. 2016; 8(7): 655-670.
48. Altaee N, Kadhim MJ, Hameed IH. Detection of volatile compounds produced by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolated from UTI patients by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. *International Journal of Current Pharmaceutical Review and Research*. 2017; 7(6).
49. Altaee N, Kadhim MJ, Hameed IH. Characterization of metabolites produced by *E. coli* and analysis of its chemical compounds using GC-MS. *International Journal of Current Pharmaceutical Review and Research*. 2017; 7(6).
50. Hussein JH, Ubaid JM, Hameed IH. Gas chromatography - mass spectrum analysis of volatile

- components of methanolic leaves extract of *Cordia myxa*. *International Journal of Current Pharmaceutical Review and Research*. 2017; 7(6).
51. Kadhim MJ, Kaizal AF, Hameed IH. Medicinal plants used for treatment of rheumatoid arthritis: A review. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*. 2017; 8(11).
52. Hameed, I.H., Al-Rubaye A.F. and Kadhim, M.J. Antimicrobial Activity of Medicinal Plants and Urinary Tract Infections. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*. 2017; 8(11).
53. Kadhim WA, Kadhim, M.J., Hameed, I.H. Antibacterial Activity of Several Plant Extracts Against *Proteus Species*. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*. 2017; 8(11).
54. Kadhim MJ. *In Vitro* antifungal potential of *Acinetobacter baumannii* and determination of its chemical composition by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. *Der Pharma Chemica*, 2016; 8(19): 657-665.
55. Al-Yaseri A, Kadhim WA, Hameed IH. Detection of volatile compounds emitted by *Proteus mirabilis* isolated from UTI patients and its anti-fungal potential. *Der Pharma Chemica*, 2016; 8(19): 671-678.
56. Ubaid JM, Kadhim MJ, Hameed IH. Study of bioactive methanolic extract of *Camponotus fellah* using Gas chromatography – mass spectrum. *International Journal of Current Pharmaceutical Review and Research*. 2017; 7(6).
57. Singh RK, Dhiman RC, Mittal PK. Studies on mosquito larvicidal properties of *Eucalyptus citriodora* Hook (family Myrtaceae). *J. Commun Diseases*. 2007; 39: 233-236.
58. Habila N, Agbaji AS, Ladan Z, Bello IA, Haruna E, Dakare MA, Atolagbe TO. Evaluation of in vitro activity of essential oils against *Trypanosoma brucei* and *Trypanosoma evansi*. *J. Parasitol Research*. 2010; 107: 534-539.
59. Ramezani H, Singh HP, Batish DR, Kohli RK, Dargan JS. Fungicidal effect of volatile oils from *Eucalyptus citriodora* and its major constituent citronellal. *New Zealand Plant Protection*. 2002; 55: 327-330.
60. Setia N, Batish DR, Singh HP, Kohli RK. Phytotoxicity of volatile oil from *Eucalyptus citriodora* against some weedy species. *J Environ Biology*. 2007; 28: 63-66.